

Psychiatry Diagnoses Coercion in Government, Towards a Unified Theory of Psychiatric Disorders

Johan Nygren, johanngrn@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: Executive function (EF) refers to the higher order cognitive processes involved in the conscious control of behavior, thought, and emotion. Impairment of the executive function characterizes all psychiatric diagnoses. This article presents the theory that subordinating the executive function of a person through coercion is a direct cause of executive dysfunction, and that the psychiatric disorders that are diagnosed by psychiatric science reflect coercion used in government.

1. Introduction

1.1 Psychiatric disorders, a unified theory

Executive function (EF) or executive control refers to the higher order cognitive processes involved in the conscious control of behavior, thought, and emotion, essential for successful navigation through a complex social world inundated with intricate norms and moral values. (Forbes, 2010) Over 2500 scientific articles have been published on this topic in the past 25 years. (Alvarez, 2006) The executive (ego) function recruits from a wide range of functional abilities that are orchestrated in part by the frontal lobes, the term “frontal functions” often used synonymously with “executive functions”. (Alvarez, 2006) Impairment of the ego function, usually defined as executive dysfunction, executive function disorder, or executive disorder in short, affects the higher order cognitive functions in this “orchestrator of the mind”, and psychiatric disorders are classified based on the severity of impairment.

1.2 Executive disorder, not mental disorder

The loss of executive function, i.e., the ability to manipulate memes, makes it difficult for the individual to absorb, process, and integrate new information. (Leigh, 2010) In medical terms, failure of the executive function can be understood as analogous to failure of any organ function. It is the paralysis of this control mechanism of the brain that defines psychiatric disorders, and it is responsible for mental illness, a secondary disease caused by executive disorder, the loss of authority over the contents of the mind.

The executive function is above the mind in a hierarchy of control, and per deductive reasoning, the term mental disorder is a causal impossibility, the equivalent of spontaneous generation theory for mental illness, and now an obsolete medical theory.

1.3 Mental illness as “meme illness”

Hoyle Leigh, psychiatrist and MD who co-founded the Yale Institute of Behavioral Medicine in the 70s, and went on to write *Genes, Memes, Culture and Mental Illness: Towards an Integrative Model* in 2010, defines mental illness in that it is caused by *pathological memes*,

and studies diseases of the mind as *memetic diseases*. (Leigh, 2010) The word mental, from Latin mentalis "of the mind," can be understood as a primitive version of meme theory, with memes being the units of information that make up the mind, the constituents of the mind. (Dawkins, 1976; Blackmore, 1999)

1.4 Executive disorder by other causes than coercion

It goes without saying that executive dysfunction can have other causes than government coercion, brain damage like in the case of Phineas P. Gage (Bigelow, 1850) being an often used example. Psychiatry is per definition the study of mental disorders, an obsolete medical theory, in this article redefined as executive disorder from coercive government.

2. Materials & Methods

2.1 Meme theory in medical science, and psychiatry

“Before Pasteur popularized the notion that bacteria cause disease, healthcare was effectively a disease vector, and we will come to look at centralized legal systems as vectors for what we have called diseases of the mind.”

The concept of disease transmission and contagion was well established before microorganisms were identified. As the conception upon diseases transmission reflects the society's state of progress, we passed from the miasma theory and spontaneous generation theory, to germ theory. (Karamanou, 2012) Likewise, the concept of meme-transmission reflects society's progress, from possessed spirits or an infection of the uterus, to the most important concept in the history of psychiatric science, the meme theory. (Dawkins, 1976; Blackmore, 1999)

2.2 Executive disorder a symptom of coercion

Subordinating the executive function of a person through coercion, under a monopoly on violence, decreases their executive control. Decreased executive control, impairment of the executive function, causes executive dysfunction. Using these propositions only, it can be proven that overruling executive control in a person causes executive dysfunction.

2.3 Meme illness a symptom of executive disorder

Impairment of the executive function from coercion decreases the brain's ability to filter and select memes, to self-regulate (Leigh, 2010), and this loss of executive control is responsible for proliferation of pathological memes and disease progression of meme illness.

2.4 Hysteria as a case study

“Never doubt that a small group of thoughtful, committed citizens can change the world. Indeed, it's the only thing that ever has.”

“Hysteria” was an executive disorder in the 19th century that affected females. The lack of female voting rights meant that females suffered more government coercion than males, with more severe impairment of the executive function. Psychiatry in the 19th century pointed the

cause of “hysteria” to the female uterus, a sex organ that distinguishes females from males, a fiction that served to legitimize social inequality between males and females. Hysteria is an ideal case study to prove the theory that psychiatry diagnoses coercion in government, because of what the Women’s Rights Movement achieved. After the war and the passage of women’s suffrage in England and the United States, it was believed that female hysteria declined and even disappeared (Gilman, 1993).

2.5 Executive disorder from coercion is somatic, not mental

Executive disorders that are caused by coercion, are a response to physical and visceral - *somatic* - pecking orders, somatic trauma that originates from genetic imperatives for dominance hierarchy behaviour in humans. (Price, 1967) This assertion is proven by the observation that physical removal of the coercive entity that causes an executive disorder will regain executive function in the individual.

The mental component in psychiatric disorders is a consequence of the loss of executive control.

2.6 Human ritual sacrifice and the social control hypothesis

The social control hypothesis (Winkelman, 2014) proposes that human sacrifice legitimizes and stabilizes a stratified society. Evidence for human sacrifice is found throughout the archaeological record of early civilization. (Watts, 2016) This begs a simple question – is there any comparable system around today to promote social stratification by human sacrifice? Psychiatric diagnoses as religious myths (Whitley, 2008) legitimize the subordination of humans who have not given consent, appeal to “objective truth” and the “will of science” to strip people of individual agency, and institute an example, a deterrent to disobedience. Psychiatry is human sacrifice to legitimize coercive government. (Moncrieff, 2010)

3. Results

3.1 Psychiatry diagnoses coercion in government

Overruling executive control in a person causes executive dysfunction, and accounts for all executive dysfunction that is diagnosed by psychiatric science.

3.2 Psychiatry is a disease vector

The field of psychiatric science, a proto-science and religion (Whitley, 2008) more than a branch of medical science, has given legitimacy to the subordination of non-consenting human beings by a master class (Whitley, 2008; Moncrieff, 2010), and stabilized master-slave type social stratification (Watts, 2016) enforced through instincts for dominance hierarchies with pecking orders (Price, 1967). This role of psychiatry as a political device (Moncrieff, 2010) has increased the prevalence of executive disorder, it has served as a disease vector that has decreased health, the exact opposite of medical science. In other

words, psychiatric disorders are nosocomial diseases, diseases whose development are favoured by a hospital environment.

3.3 The cure for executive disorder and meme illness

The evidence that executive disorder is caused by coercion, and that meme illness results from a loss of executive control, opens the door to a new form of treatment for psychiatric disorders. It can be shown, beyond any reasonable doubt, that physical removal of the coercive entity that causes an executive disorder, will return executive control to the patient and alleviate all symptoms, curing the executive disorder.

That should be the role of the medical doctor, and psychiatric science, going forwards.

4. Conclusion

Executive disorder is caused by coercion, decreasing the brain's ability to filter and select memes, causing "meme illness", a symptom of loss of executive control, and psychiatric disorders are classified based on the severity of impairment. The conclusion of this unified theory of psychiatric disorders must be to go further than just point to where psychiatry failed, and to instead look at how it could be redeemed. To ask the question: could the "medical gaze" (Foucault, 1963) be re-focused, and rehumanize instead of dehumanize? Science as a protocol is not a map but a compass, and like germ theory led to a revolution in healthcare, meme theory could raise medical science out of mind-body dualism, and return executive control to the individual.

References

Forbes, Chad & Grafman, Jordan. (2010). The Role of the Human Prefrontal Cortex in Social Cognition and Moral Judgment *. *Annual review of neuroscience*. 33. 299-324. 10.1146/annurev-neuro-060909-153230.

Alvarez, J. A., & Emory, E. (2006). Executive Function and the Frontal Lobes: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Neuropsychology Review*, 16(1), 17–42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11065-006-9002-x>

Leigh, H., & Leigh, H. (2010). *Genes, Memes, Culture, and Mental Illness*. Springer New York. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-5671-2>

Dawkins, Richard. (1978, ©1976) *The selfish gene* /New York : Oxford University Press.

Blackmore, S. J. (1999). *The meme machine*. Oxford [England]: Oxford University Press.

Bigelow, Henry Jacob (1850). Dr. Harlow's case of Recovery from the passage of an Iron Bar through the Head. *American Journal of the Medical Sciences* 20:13–22 (Republished in Macmillan 2000).

Karamanou, Marianna & Panayiotakopoulos, George & Tsoucalas, Gregory & Kousoulis, Antonis & Androutsos, George. (2012). From miasmas to germs: A historical approach to theories of infectious disease transmission. *Le Infezioni in Medicina*, n. 1, 52-56.

Gilman, S. (1993). *Hysteria before Freud*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Price, J. (1967). THE DOMINANCE HIERARCHY AND THE EVOLUTION OF MENTAL ILLNESS. *The Lancet*, 290(7509), 243–246. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(67\)92306-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(67)92306-9)

Winkelman, M. (2014). Political and Demographic-Ecological Determinants of Institutionalised Human Sacrifice. *Anthropological Forum*, 24(1), 47–70. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00664677.2014.860888>

Watts, J., Sheehan, O., Atkinson, Q. D., Bulbulia, J., & Gray, R. D. (2016). Ritual human sacrifice promoted and sustained the evolution of stratified societies. *Nature*, 532(7598), 228–231. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature17159>

Whitley, R. (2008). Is psychiatry a religion? *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 101(12), 579–582. <https://doi.org/10.1258/jrsm.2008.080044>

Moncrieff, J. (2010). Psychiatric diagnosis as a political device. *Social Theory & Health*, 8(4), 370–382. <https://doi.org/10.1057/sth.2009.11>

Foucault, M. (1963). *Naissance de la clinique: Une archéologie du regard médical*. Paris: Presses universitaires de France.